

1 **CXADR expression defines embryonic stem cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 East Islip, NY USA 11730
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 Embryonic stem cells are functionally defined by pluripotency, or the ability to differentiate into cell and
6 tissue types of the three germ layers and to self-renew. Genes like *Nanog* have been described that
7 support the development of or mark the embryonic state, but the complete transcriptional state of the
8 human embryonic stem cell remains to be completely defined. We identified the most significant
9 transcriptional features of the embryonic stem cell by measuring and comparing total transcription in
10 differentiated cell types, fibroblasts and keratinocytes, and the human embryonic stem cell. We describe
11 here expression of *CXADR* as a defining transcriptional property of human ES cells. Concomitant with
12 *CXADR* expression in hES was silencing of the *CXADR*-like membrane protein *CLMP*. *CXADR* was
13 co-regulated with activin receptor pathway component *ACVR2A*; we identified *ACVR2B* as an embryonic
14 stem cell gene.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Results

We measured total transcription in human embryonic stem cells, or in induced pluripotent stem cells, as well as in fibroblasts to understand the defining transcriptional characteristics of the embryonic stem cell.

Figure 1: CXADR is an embryonic stem cell gene.

GSE224698: fibroblasts v hES

n=3 fibroblasts (human dermal)

n=2 human embryonic stem cells (H9 and KhES)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1525	1.61e-29	0.394	-11.282206	-4.4432913	3045.58	CXADR	556/20137	97.2
79827	1.18e-17	0.407	8.5550174	3.484613	7606.68	CLMP	1331/20137	93.4

We observed repression of the CXADR-like membrane protein CLMP concomitant with CXADR induction in hES (Figure 1).

Figure 2: CXADR is transcriptionally activated in induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS), and CXADR-like membrane protein CLMP is repressed in iPS.

GSE221827: fibroblasts v iPS

n=2 human foreskin fibroblasts

n=2 induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1525	0.00	0.1183	-40.268944	-4.762695	1527.27	CXADR	272/18330	98.5
79827	0.00	0.0928	44.332142	4.114512	2989.41	CLMP	183/18330	99.0

Figure 3: CXADR induction and CLMP repression is a shared transcriptional feature of iPS and hES.

GSE216689: fibroblast v (hiPS and hES)

n=1 fibroblast

n=2 iPS cell and ES cell (H9)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1525	3.47e-55	0.323	-15.647311	-5.052032	4306.58	CXADR	189/23756	99.2
79827	3.64e-15	0.347	7.86682	2.726739	3006.62	CLMP	1377/23756	94.2

To gain insight into the role CXADR plays in embryonic stem cells, we studied transcriptional co-regulation across human cells and tissues using SEEK.

We found that CXADR was transcriptionally co-regulated with ACVR2A. Measuring total transcription in hES and differentiated cells, we identified ACVR2B as an embryonic stem cell gene. We concluded that the activin receptor pathway likely functions in pluripotency.

Figure 4: The activin receptor pathway component ACVR2A is co-regulated with CXADR.

Figure 5: ACVR2B is an embryonic stem cell gene.

GSE221827: fibroblasts v iPS

n=2 human foreskin fibroblasts

n=2 induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
93	0.00	0.1117	-42.173618	-4.712162	1616.39	ACVR2B	53/18330	

Discussion

We identified here the Ig-like cell adhesion molecule *CXADR* as an embryonic stem cell gene.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We measured total transcription in embryonic stem cells and in induced pluripotent stem cells using the aforementioned publicly available or published datasets and R-based computational methods. We performed transcriptional co-regulation analysis using SEEK.